

FOR GETTING MORE LIFE SATISFACTION BEING A CHOIR SINGER IN GOLDEN YEARSⁱ

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Abstract:

The main aim of this study is to determine the profile of choir singer in golden years (CSGY), to compare motivational factors with respect to some demographic variables and how effect being of a CSGY's life satisfaction in their golden years. This research is descriptive and population consists of 37 nonprofessional choir's choir singers taken from 43 total choirs in Antalya city center. In this study, the questionnaire was handed to retired 174 men ($X_{age}=62.58\pm 7.20$), 198 women ($X_{age}=57.87\pm 6.07$) total 372 choir singers. In this study, the designed questionnaire addresses demographic variables, The Satisfaction with Life Scale-(SWLS) developed by Diener et al. (1985) adapted in to Turkish by Yetim (1993), and The Motivational Factors Scale of being Choir Singer (MFSC) developed by Ardahan (2016a), and benefit lists. The LS data of non-choir singers, 113 man, 183 women total 296 persons who never sing/been in a choir before, was taken from Ardahan's study (2016b). In addition to this, running period data, benefits and motivational factor's score of individuals who were still working/be employed somewhere were taken from Ardahan and Akdeniz's study (2017a). In the processing of assessing data the descriptive statistic methods, Independent Samples T Test, ANOVA Test, and Pearson Correlations Test have been used, results have been assessed according to significant level 0.01 and 0.05. The findings show that majority of choir singers were 60 years old and more, attend to Turkish Art Music Choir, married, belong to a choir, well educated, have 700\$ or below monthly income, retired, living with family husband/wife/children, going choir alone, pay due, participate passive recreational activities and the major motivational factors for attending to choir were Liking Music, Relaxing as Mentally, Renovate and/or Developed, Socialization, Exemplifying, To be away and/or Escape, and Recognition and Social status. As a result, it can be said that individuals going to a choir in their golden years for Liking Music, Relaxing as Mentally, Renovate and/or Developed, Socialization, Exemplifying, to be

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away and/or Escape, and Recognition and Social status and create globally wellness and happiness in their life.

Keywords: choir; choir singer, golden age, motivational factors, recreational activity

1. Introduction

There are several corners in social and professional career of individuals, like the first step when a baby, graduating from high school and starting university when young, graduation ceremony for university, getting married, divorcing, being parents, being retired, being grandfather/mother etc. It's like climbing up stairs. Being retired can be accepted as a main corner of individual's life which determines a pass from middle age to old age, it is end of professional life (Kılavuz, 2002).

Retirement has five dimensions. These are a) legal dimension, b) economic dimension explain loss of economic power, c) physiological dimension, d) psychological dimension, and e) social dimension. When professional life ends with retirement, individuals have lots of free time, but many of them loss their economic power, social power and status, physical healthy, energy, productivity, change their way of life. If individuals do not make enough investment like home, materials, car, money, income-generating investments etc., golden years will be restrictive (Şen, 2015). In many countries, retired period can be defined as absolute poverty and/or perceived poverty period. To decrease the negative effect of poverty, many individuals usually delay retiring or after retirement usually continue working in same or different job (Kılavuz, 2002). On the other hand, this period can be accepted an opportunity period for realization of postponed life/things. Professional career and social career as getting married, being parents, many other social roles and hobbies contemporaneously continue and usually there is conflict between these two roles. Individuals give their attention/priority to their professional roles for earning necessary money for life, for getting social and economic power. And usually, they delay their own life including hobbies and/or social life. After retirement, people focus on their delayed social life and personal preferences (Karadeniz and Öztepe, 2013).

Social dimension of retirement is the most important part for individual's recreational life. After long and tiring professional life, retirement gives individuals lots of free time and opportunities that can be used for enrichment of recreational life including socialization. Usually many individuals dream long and/or overseas journeys, living in a chalet or a firm life with gardening, farming, and give opportunity to learn new hobbies or realize delayed hobbies/things. This is the positive face of retirement. In the beginning, having long free time seems to be pleasurable for all, but later many can find it boring. Some turn to their old hobbies for activating them or some try to create new hobbies. And usually, individuals make preferences among hobbies because of poverty of retirement.

Researchers accept that golden age hobbies are usually serious leisure activities and/or sometimes project-based leisure. Amateur or volunteer choirs are one of the

good forms of serious and/or project-based leisure (Tipps, 2003). Serious leisure activities can be amateur, hobbyist and volunteer which participant finds interesting, substantial, and create his/her social career that can support professional career by using their own knowledge, special skills and experience (Stebbins, 1992). At the same time, serious leisure activities can be accepted as one of the most efficient way of learning, using and/or developing skills (Stebbins, 1982). While amateurs were in science, sport, art, entertainment with professional approach, in contrast, hobbyists and volunteers lack the professional alter ego of amateurs (Stebbins, 2007). Project-based leisure is a short-term which can be one-shot or sporadic carried out in free time for support a social project (Stebbins, 2005).

Main aim of professional choirs was usually economic, amateur or volunteer choirs are for a sociological and/or for supporting a social project. Stebbins defines amateur choir as a structure formed by amateur individuals have limited knowledge of music with professional expectation (Stebbins, 1992). In addition to these, Stebbins defines music as opportunity for learning/training skills, center of someone's social life to generate their social career, a tool or objective for realizing their life for the individuals whose hobbies are music (Stebbins, 1982).

Usually individuals, especially in golden age individuals, do not change or abandon from their idea, social relations with his/her social groups, culture and religion, and try to run them all through their life, if they do not have any conflict, or any other problems (Bell, 2000). A choir is a form of belonging to a group or social structure (Ardahan and Akdeniz, 2017a) and individuals get pleasure to keep on music in their life whether singing or making music. Dabble in making music, singing in amateur choirs make individuals happy because of the therapeutic effect of music. Silverman concludes that music have positive effect on fight against addiction (Silverman, 2003). Some mode of Turkish Art Music has been using for rehabilitation for some physical, psychological illness (Ak, 1997). Rast Mode gives pleasure, Rehavi Mode gives oceanic feeling, Zırgüle mode gives sleeping feeling, Hüseyini mode strengths relaxing, Saba mode strengths braveness feeling and so on.

Heo et al. claims individuals get satisfaction and pleasure, when they have active or passive participation in to the leisure activities (Heo et al. 2013). Singing in an amateur choir is an active participation to the recreational life, listening/watching a concert is a passive form of leisure. In addition to these, music is a tool and/or purpose of rehabilitation and it has positive effect on physical, mental and emotional health and wellness (Ardahan and Akdeniz, 2017b).

All individuals' expectation from their professional and social life are being happy, having wellbeing, wellness and satisfaction. Happiness, wellbeing, wellness and satisfaction seem to be same but they have different meanings. Happiness is fulfillments of individual's needsⁱⁱⁱ. It is getting pleasure from life and having a well lived life and called scientifically subjective wellbeing^{iv}.

ⁱⁱⁱ - <http://happinessinternational.org/what-is-happiness/#sthash.7CqPNmCe.dpbs>, retrieved in 19/05/2017.

^{iv} - <http://www.newstatesman.com/lifestyle/2015/07/pursuit-happiness-what-happiness-and-how-can-we-make-ourselves-happier>, retrieved in 19/05/2017.

Wellbeing is the state of healthy, vitality, being happy or comfortable in individual's life^v. Wellness is "the active process of becoming aware of and making choices toward a healthy and fulfilling life"^{vi} and World Health Organization (WHO) (WHO, 2014) defines wellness as "a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being, and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity".

Satisfaction has many classifications like Life Satisfaction (LS), Social Satisfaction, Role and Marital Satisfaction, Professional and Economic Satisfaction, Emotional Satisfaction, Leisure Satisfaction, Job Satisfaction, and etc. Satisfaction can be defined as realization level of expectations (Ardahan, 2016a). All these satisfaction effect other satisfactions and affected from them. At the same time, all these satisfactions affect and affected from individual's physical, mental, emotional life, professional and social interaction (Ardahan, 2014). LS can be defined as the sensation and/or decision of individual's life, emotional attitude toward his/her life and can be measured by the realization level of expectations. LS effect and effected from many other things like physical, mental and emotional health, having a) meaningful relation and/or interaction with partner, wife/husband, children, friends, collages, family member, relatives and others, b) sufficient income for all expectations, satisfactory job or professional life, c) emotional, physical and mental wellness, positive personality, d) satisfactorily equipped neighborhood/environment, e) pleasure retrieved from social and/or professional life, e) material things, f) hobbies, enough time to realize hobbies, opportunity to participate recreational activities, g) high quality of life, and many other thing (Diener et al. 1985; Diener, 1984; Pavot and Diener, 1993).

Happiness is not a) feeling good all the time, b) being economically rich or having economic power to afford every want, c) final destination. Researchers suggest that happiness is combination of how satisfied with the life and it is the only reality and the meanings of living. If individuals are not happy life, he/she cannot have satisfied, or vice versa. So, the things effect being satisfaction, wellbeing and wellness is important for being happy. For example, high income, living in a house with good scene, being married with a beautiful woman make individuals satisfied but these do not make us happier. Being happy have positive effect on satisfaction. Their meanings of these words are different but they have interactive relation.

Dabble in making music, singing in amateur choirs, it has positive effect on socialization, developing skills or learn new ones, renovation, being away from daily routine, home and work escape from something, recognition and social status (Ardahan, 2016a). If something/someone seriously chosen or casually happen has positive effect on one's feelings/life, it makes happy. Singing can be a casual, project based or serious leisure activity. If it is casual, it causes short time happiness, if project based leisure; it causes midterm happiness. But if serious leisure, it creates way of life and long term happiness (Stebbins, 1992).

^v - <http://www.nationalaccountsofwellbeing.org/learn/what-is-well-being.html>, retrieved in 19/05/2017.

^{vi} - <https://shcs.ucdavis.edu/wellness/what-is-wellness>, retrieved in 19/05/2017.

2. Method

The main aim of this study is to determine the profile of choir singer in golden years (CSGY), to compare motivational factors with respect to some demographic variables and how effect being of a CSGY's life satisfaction (LS) in their golden years.

This research is descriptive and the scope of this study is restricted to recreational choir singers in city center of Antalya. Sampling group of this study consists of 372 choir singers of 37 amateur choirs. The exact number of the choirs in Center of Antalya was 43 and six choirs excluded from study because, two of them were professional and four of them did not want to join to survey.

The questionnaire was handed to retired 174 men ($X_{age}=62.58\pm 7.20$), 198 women ($X_{age}=57.87\pm 6.07$) total 372 choir singers. The designed questionnaire addresses demographic variables, and The Satisfaction with Life Scale-(SWLS) developed by Diener et al. (1985) adapted in to Turkish by Yetim (1993) and The Motivational Factors Scale of Being Choir Singer (MFSCSGY) developed by Ardahan (2016a) was used. A five-point Likert scale was used for scales and benefit items and the range covers (1: definitely disagree, 5: definitely agree). In this study, the questionnaire was handed to all choir singers and collected back in 15 minutes. The LS data of non-choir singers, 113 man, 183 women total 296 persons who never sing/been in a choir before, was taken from Ardahan's study (2016b). In addition to this, running period data, benefits and motivational factor's score of individuals who were still working/be employed somewhere were taken from Ardahan and Akdeniz's study (2017a). In the processing of assessing data the descriptive statistic methods, Independent Samples t Test, ANOVA Test, and Pearson Correlations Test have been used, results have been assessed according to significant level 0.01 and 0.05.

3. Findings

The profile of choir singers in golden age (CSGY) and comparison of the motivational factor effect individuals run to recreational choir as a choir singer and life satisfaction (LS) with respect to some demographic variables were given in this part.

The profile of CSGY age was given in Table 1. As it seen in table; majority of the CSGY run to Turkish Art Music Choir and Organizational Choir, women, married, running choirs more than two or more years, living with family members/husband/wife/children, have personal monthly income 700\$ or below, family monthly income 1050\$ or below, running choir alone, well educated, running only one choir in a season, paying due, 60 years old or more, spend about four hours for running choir in a week, average running periods to choirs were about 7.75 ± 8.99 years, and has life satisfaction level 3.47 ± 0.81 . When compared LS level of CSGY (3.47 ± 0.81) and Non-Chorist Singers (3.11 ± 0.87), there is strongly meaningful difference in favor of CSGY. This means that participating choir as a singer increase LS level of participants.

Table 1: Chorist Profile

Choir Type	n	%	Choir Form	n	%
Turkish Folk Music	116	31.2	NGO Choir	37	9.9
Turkish Art Music	256	68.8	Organizational Choir	189	50.8
Gender	n	%	Private Choir	146	39.2
Man	174	46.8	Marital Status	n	%
Women	198	53.2	Married	267	71.8
Running Period	n	%	Single	105	28.2
1 year and less	81	21.8	Living With Whom	n	%
2-4 years	110	29.6	Alone	74	19.9
5-10 years	101	27.2	With family members	134	36.0
11 years and more	80	21.5	With my husband/wife/Children	161	43.3
Personal Monthly Income	n	%	With friends	3	0.8
350\$ and below	20	5.4	Family Monthly Income	n	%
351-700\$	202	54.3	350\$ and below	12	3.2
701-1050\$	101	27.2	351-700\$	104	28.0
1051-1400\$	29	7.8	701-1050\$	121	32.5
1401 \$ and more	20	5.4	1051-1400\$	59	15.9
Running Choir With Whom	n	%	1401-1750\$	45	12.1
Alone	247	66.4	1751\$ and more	31	8.3
With family members	66	17.7	Education	n	%
With friends	59	15.9	Primary School	23	6.2
How many different choir	n	%	High School	136	36.6
One	225	60.5	University	161	43.3
Two	96	25.8	Master or Doctorate	52	14.0
Three or more	51	13.8	Paying Due	n	%
Age	n	%	Paying	275	73.9
59 years old and below	170	45.7	Free	97	26.1
60 years and more	202	54.3	Total	372	100.0
Comparison of LS	X±SD	t	Spend Time for Choir in a week	4.09±3.11	
LS of Retired Choir Singer	3.47±0.81	t = 5.372*	Average age	60.08±7.02	
LS of Non-Choir Singer	3.13±0.88		Average Running Period (year)	7.75±8.99	

PS: Currency rate is 1\$= 2.85 TL and minimum wage is 456\$ in Turkey in June 2016

The recreational activities of CSGY were given in Table 2. As it seen in table; majority of them prefer cultural and art activities rather than sportive recreational activities. Their favorite cultural and art activities are being interested in music, going cinema, going theatre. At the same time, they prefer watching TV, be in with family, resting at home and surfing in internet. Their sportive recreational activities are outdoor sports like trekking, hiking, foresting, water sports like swimming and recreational activities in City Park.

Table 2: Other Recreational Activities of CSGY

Cultural and Art Activities	n	%	Sportive Activities	n	%
Being interested in music	261	70.2	Outdoor Sports	115	30.9
Watching TV	226	60.8	Water Sports	83	22.3
Be in with family	209	56.2	Recreational Activities in City Parks	45	12.1
Resting at home	178	47.8	Sports in Fitness Center	44	11.8
Surfing in internet	189	50.8	Folk and Sportive Dance	37	9.9

Going to cinema	187	50.3	Racket Sports	19	5.1
Going to theatre	164	44.1	Team Sports	18	4.8
Shopping	160	43.0	Individual Sports	15	4.0
Being interested in handicraft	125	33.6	Moto Sports	7	1.9
Being in social media	71	19.1	Struggle sports	4	1.1
Being interested in photography	32	8.6	Air Sports	3	0.8

Table 3: Comparison of Motivational Factors and Life Satisfaction with Respect to Some Demographic Variables

Factors ► Demographic Variables ▼	Renovate / Developed	Relaxing As Mentally	To be away Escape	Socialization	Liking Music	Recognition and Social status	Exemplifying	Life Satisfaction
Choir Type (t)	1.341	1.348	0.751	1.716	1.756	1.203	1.778	1.644
Folk Music	4.00±0.79	4.12±0.76	2.80±1.18	3.52±0.91	4.38±0.76	2.85±1.13	3.46±1.25	3.56±0.78
Art Music	3.87±0.94	3.99±0.88	2.70±1.15	3.34±0.96	4.23±0.80	2.69±1.16	3.21±1.19	3.42±0.82
Choir Form (F)	2.604	4.031*	9.153*	1.960	2.146	10.971*	7.333*	0.762
NGO	3.71±0.91	3.76±1.07	2.72±1.12	3.15±0.95	4.02±0.96	2.60±1.20	2.63±1.29	3.36±0.96
Organizational	3.86±0.90	3.98±0.84	2.50±1.09	3.37±0.93	4.32±0.67	2.51±1.10	3.27±1.25	3.44±0.77
Private	4.04±0.88	4.16±0.76	3.04±1.19	3.49±0.97	4.29±0.88	3.08±1.13	3.48±1.10	3.52±0.82
Gender (t)	0.163	-1.856	0.090	-0.113	-0.409	2.593*	0.159	-0.951
Man	3.92±0.83	3.95±0.83	2.74±1.22	3.39±0.95	4.26±0.78	2.90±1.12	3.30±1.26	3.42±0.83
Women	3.91±0.96	4.11±0.85	2.73±1.11	3.40±0.96	4.29±0.80	2.60±1.16	3.28±1.18	3.50±0.79
Marital Status (t)	0.330	0.830	-0.411	1.213	0.684	1.072	2.973*	0.080
Married	3.92±0.88	4.06±0.83	2.72±1.16	3.43±0.93	4.29±0.79	2.78±1.11	3.41±1.21	3.47±0.81
Single	3.89±0.94	3.97±0.86	2.77±1.17	3.30±0.99	4.23±0.80	2.64±1.25	3.00±1.19	3.46±0.81
Age (t)	1.458	2.002*	-1.959*	-0.847	0.890	-3.360*	0.463	-0.666
59 <=	3.99±0.88	4.13±0.79	2.60±1.12	3.35±0.88	4.32±0.74	2.52±1.11	3.32±1.16	3.43±0.80
60 >=	3.85±0.91	3.95±0.87	2.84±1.18	3.43±1.00	4.24±0.83	2.92±1.16	3.26±1.26	3.49±0.82
Education (F)	1.040	0.106	2.289	1.055	0.638	5.161*	3.593*	0.914
Primary School	4.18±0.75	4.01±0.85	3.00±1.24	3.60±1.14	4.45±0.67	3.32±1.29	3.47±1.27	3.71±0.91
High School	3.93±0.96	4.00±0.89	2.88±1.16	3.47±0.98	4.25±0.87	2.92±1.10	3.49±1.09	3.41±0.86
University	3.91±0.83	4.06±0.82	2.64±1.16	3.35±0.92	4.25±0.75	2.52±1.14	3.23±1.25	3.47±0.75
Postgraduate	3.78±0.98	4.04±0.83	2.49±1.08	3.26±0.88	4.35±0.74	2.72±1.11	2.88±1.28	3.49±0.82
Personal Income (F)	0.251	0.784	1.574	0.890	0.719	0.189	1.682	3.124*
350\$ and below	3.94±0.83	3.91±0.88	3.05±1.05	3.53±0.88	4.30±0.70	2.90±1.30	3.35±1.10	3.37±0.90
351-700\$	3.88±0.94	4.05±0.85	2.83±1.16	3.44±1.00	4.30±0.77	2.75±1.16	3.43±1.18	3.47±0.83
701-1050\$	3.92±0.85	3.96±0.80	2.59±1.18	3.32±0.78	4.22±0.85	2.73±1.15	3.12±1.23	3.32±0.76
1051-1400\$	4.00±0.84	4.06±0.94	2.51±1.09	3.17±1.00	4.15±0.82	2.62±0.99	3.11±1.20	3.71±0.57
1401 \$ and more	4.06±0.95	4.30±0.78	2.50±1.13	3.55±1.14	4.48±0.76	2.70±1.20	2.96±1.52	3.92±0.85
Family Income (F)	1.434	1.390	1.659	0.744	0.768	2.069	0.819	3.008*
350\$ and below	4.14±0.71	4.02±0.58	3.48±1.20	3.81±0.70	4.25±0.66	3.41±1.23	3.86±0.71	3.78±0.85
351-700\$	3.92±0.88	3.95±0.90	2.80±1.12	3.40±1.01	4.29±0.70	2.85±1.16	3.32±1.21	3.32±0.84
701-1050\$	3.99±0.91	4.04±0.81	2.76±1.20	3.44±0.95	4.28±0.84	2.80±1.17	3.26±1.21	3.49±0.83
1051-1400\$	3.64±0.91	3.91±0.90	2.67±1.23	3.34±0.85	4.17±0.82	2.62±1.18	3.25±1.23	3.43±0.79
1401-1750\$	3.95±0.80	4.20±0.68	2.60±1.07	3.30±0.90	4.23±0.86	2.43±1.03	3.11±1.25	3.39±0.71
1751\$ and more	3.97±1.04	4.29±0.93	2.43±1.04	3.27±1.05	4.51±0.79	2.53±1.03	3.43±1.34	3.90±0.63
Living With (F)	0.340	2.442	0.210	2.133	1.127	1.320	2.000	0.855
Alone	3.89±0.97	3.90±0.90	2.80±1.18	3.25±1.04	4.30±0.73	2.62±1.27	2.98±1.20	3.44±0.86
Family members	3.90±0.89	3.95±0.90	2.69±1.15	3.46±0.95	4.19±0.96	2.89±1.11	3.38±1.20	3.52±0.72
Hus./Wife/ Children	3.93±0.88	4.17±0.75	2.73±1.16	3.38±0.90	4.34±0.65	2.67±1.11	3.36±1.21	3.43±0.85
Friends	4.41±0.52	3.85±0.51	3.00±1.33	4.50±0.50	4.66±0.57	3.08±1.80	3.44±2.14	2.86±1.00
Running With (F)	0.488	0.804	1.129	0.771	0.104	2.242	1.211	0.190
Alone	3.95±0.89	4.12±0.81	2.54±0.90	3.39±0.94	4.24±0.93	2.47±1.05	3.36±1.24	3.51±0.65
Family members	3.88±0.90	3.99±0.86	2.77±1.23	3.36±0.98	4.29±0.79	2.80±1.20	3.23±1.25	3.45±0.86

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Friends	4.01±0.91	4.10±0.80	2.80±1.11	3.53±0.85	4.27±0.62	2.78±1.04	3.49±1.01	3.48±0.75
Paying Due (t)	1.381	0.851	1.231	-0.626	-0.151	2.108*	-0.164	0.660
Paying	3.95±0.89	4.05±0.85	2.78±1.22	3.38±0.98	4.27±0.80	2.82±1.18	3.28±1.24	3.48±0.84
Free	3.80±0.91	3.97±0.83	2.61±0.94	3.45±0.85	4.29±0.77	2.53±1.04	3.31±1.16	3.42±0.72
Running Period (F)	0.678	0.911	0.202	0.421	2.071	1.165	0.386	0.647
1 year and less	3.84±0.90	4.06±0.78	2.73±1.00	3.45±0.79	4.18±0.86	2.83±1.06	3.41±1.11	3.49±0.78
2-4 years	3.88±0.88	3.98±0.81	2.68±1.06	3.33±0.98	4.21±0.79	2.57±1.17	3.23±1.20	3.54±0.71
5-10 years	4.02±0.90	4.13±0.87	2.80±1.30	3.37±1.00	4.44±0.60	2.76±1.18	3.29±1.23	3.38±0.79
11 years and more	3.90±0.92	3.95±0.91	2.71±1.26	3.46±1.00	4.27±0.90	2.85±1.17	3.25±1.34	3.44±0.97
Different Choir (F)	2.964*	1.686	2.883*	0.148	1.374	4.770*	0.747	2.202
One	3.84±0.94	3.97±0.89	2.62±1.08	3.38±0.92	4.23±0.84	2.61±1.14	3.24±1.22	3.40±0.82
Two	3.97±0.81	4.08±0.75	2.93±1.20	3.39±1.06	4.32±0.72	2.84±1.12	3.31±1.23	3.51±0.78
Three or more	4.16±0.82	4.20±0.78	2.88±1.35	3.46±0.88	4.41±0.69	3.13±1.19	3.47±1.20	3.65±0.78
Working Status (t)	-1.454	-2.290*	-0.532	0.860	-1.558	2.003*	0.621	0.850
Retired	3.91±0.90	4.03±0.84	2.73±1.16	3.39±0.95	4.28±0.79	2.74±1.15	3.29±1.22	3.46±0.81
Still Working	4.03±0.84	4.20±0.74	2.79±1.07	3.32±0.97	4.38±0.69	2.52±1.26	3.22±1.28	3.40±0.82

* p< 0.05

Comparisons of motivational factors and LS of CSGY with respect to some demographic variables were given in Table 3. As it seen in table; there are no statistically meaningful differences in motivational factors and LS with respect to Choir Type, running period, Running Choir with whom and Living with whom variables. But personal and family income variable create statistically meaningful difference only in LS not in motivational factors. When income increases, LS increases also. And income does not create any statistically meaningful difference in motivational factors.

There are statistically meaningful differences in Relaxing as Mentally, to be away/Escape, Recognition and Social status, and Exemplifying sub factors in favor of Private choirs. The mission of NGO and Organizational Choirs carry same mission of NGO and Organization itself, but private choirs can easily arrange, make necessity changes in their mission and structure/design of choir and it has positive effect on preferability and social closeness.

Table 4: Comparison of Running Period with Respect to Some Demographic Variables

Choir Type	X±SD	t	Choir Form	X±SD	F
Turkish Folk Music	7.71±8.87	-0.054	NGO Choir	8.00±7.57	0.017
Turkish Art Music	7.76±9.07		Organizational Choir	7.75±8.39	
Gender	X±SD	t	Private Choir	7.69±10.07	
Man	9.55±10.42	3.687*	Living with Whom	X±SD	F
Women	6.16±7.18		Alone	7.22±8.02	0.184
Personal Monthly Income	X±SD	F	With family members	7.91±9.42	
350\$ and below	5.65±3.75	0.879	With my husband/wife/Children	7.9±9.16	
351-700\$	8.07±9.47		With friends	5.33±4.50	
701-1050\$	6.91±8.44		Family Monthly Income	X±SD	F
1051-1400\$	8.37±9.52		350\$ and below	7.50±9.49	0.461
1401 \$ and more	9.90±9.66		351-700\$	8.59±10.33	
How many different choir	X±SD	F	701-1050\$	7.25±8.14	
One	5.93±7.50	12.732*	1051-1400\$	6.76±7.35	
Two	10.09±9.64		1401-1750\$	7.88±9.15	
Three or more	11.37±11.53		1751\$ and more	8.64±10.13	
Age	X±SD	t	Education	X±SD	F

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59 years old and below	5.86±7.03	-3.894*	Primary School	5.17±5.26	3.701*
60 years and more	9.34±10.11		High School	7.27±8.03	
Paying Due	X±SD	t	University	7.36±8.62	
Paying	8.77±9.64	3.752*	Master or Doctorate	11.34±12.47	
Free	4.85±5.97		Marital Status	X±SD	t
Attending with Whom	X±SD	F	Married	8.04±9.41	1.922*
Alone	8.39±10.93	1.485	Single	4.85±6.39	
With family members	8.01±8.72		Working Status (t)	X±SD	t
With friends	5.93±7.55		Retired	7.75±9.00	0.529
* p< 0.05			Still Working	7.36±7.47	

Gender and marital status are not a strong determiner on motivational factors of CSGY and LS. There are only statistically meaningful differences in Recognition and Social status sub factor in favor of man and in Exemplifying sub factor in favor of married. Being parents force individuals as example or idol for their children, family member and others. This were expected behavior in Turkish culture in last three or four decades. But nowadays this obligation is losing effect.

Age variable create statistically meaningful difference in three sub factor. While 59 and below years old CSGY were preferring choir for Relaxing as Mentally, 60 and more years old CSGY prefer choir for being away/Escape, Recognition and Social status. Education variable has positive effect statistically meaningful difference on Recognition and Social status, and Exemplifying sub factors low level educated CSGY. When education level decreases individuals, prefer running a choir as CSGY for Recognition and Social status, and Exemplifying. The reason of these can be that, exemplifying has been an expected behavior of primary and high school graduated CSGY, and primary school graduated CSGY could not find enough possibility to satisfactorily recognition and social status in their professional and/or social career.

Paying due has statistically meaningful difference in Recognition and Social status sub factor. Individuals willing to pay for running choir and this bring them recognition and social status or vice versa, willing to pay for recognition and social status and running choir for this reason.

Running more than one choir does not have positive effect on LS, but it has statistically meaningful difference on Renovate/Developed, to be away/Escape, and Recognition and Social status sub factors. When CSGY want to run more than one choir, their expectation for Renovate/Developed, to be away/Escape, and Recognition and Social status increase also.

Comparisons of running period with respect to some demographic variables were given in Table 4. As it seen in table; when the numbers of choirs run by CSGY, education level and age increase, running period of CSGY statistically increases also. In addition to this, man's running period to the choir is more than women, and paying due and being married have positive effect for running to choir more. There is not statistically meaningful effect on Choir Form, Personal and Family Monthly Income, Living with Whom, Attending with Whom and Working Status on running period.

Table 5: The Benefit List, Correlation with LS and Comparison of Retired (R) and Still Working (SW) CSGY's Benefits

The Benefits	LS	R	SW	t
	X ²	X±SD	X±SD	
Felt happier	0.424**	4.22±1.00	4.26±0.91	-0.521
Make new friendship	0.499**	4.15±0.98	4.21±0.91	-0.692
Improved my skills	0.468**	4.13±1.08	4.27±0.86	-1.524
Felt comforted and refreshed	0.521**	4.08±1.02	4.07±0.99	0.196
Spent my free time more qualified and productive	0.492**	4.00±1.04	4.11±0.93	-1.216
Felt satisfaction	0.381**	3.92±1.08	3.89±1.11	0.364
My musical knowledge increased	0.252**	3.89±1.30	3.96±1.23	-0.618
My self-confidence increased	0.370**	3.85±1.16	3.74±1.18	1.010
Belong to a group	0.364**	3.83±1.11	3.80±1.13	0.197
I succeed to be away from sameness, boredom, and stress	0.358**	3.79±1.27	3.79±3.65	1.186
My productivity increased	0.424**	3.75±1.10	3.91±1.09	-1.501
My dream widened	0.433**	3.65±1.17	3.69±1.21	-0.351
Get rid of loneliness	0.359**	3.48±1.32	3.19±1.36	2.353*

** p< 0.01, *p< 0.05

The declared benefit lists of CSGY were given in Table 5. As it seen in table; all benefits have higher score and the first fifth benefits in order are Felt happier, make new friendship, Improved skills, felt comforted and refreshed, and spend their free time more qualified and productive. All benefits are positive and they have positive correlation with LS. When compared benefits of BC with respect to working status (Retirement, Still Working), there is statistically meaningful difference only in one benefit, get rid of loneliness in favor of retired CSGY. This means can be that CSGY are running choir for getting rid of loneliness.

4. Conclusion

It can be concluded that majority of CSGY are willing to run Turkish Art Music Choirs because of the therapeutical effect of Turkish Art Music. This results overlaps by the results of Sezer's study (2011).

Constitute and sustain a choir is not easy. It needs financial, organizational, human-resource allocation and managerial effort. In this study the findings shows that CSGY have long term continuousness to the choir. Because of this they prefer organizational and private choirs to achieve sustainability. And the majority of CSGY support their choir organization by paying due. The result show that, paying due CSGY has running period to choirs than others. Choir type is important for flexibility. Private choirs can be easily designed than others and creates more satisfaction to members. The advantaged motivational factors for running to a private choir are Relaxing as mentally, to be away/Escape, Recognition and Social Status and Exemplifying.

In contrast to outdoor recreational activities, there is women's hegemony in amateur choirs (Ardahan, 2011a, 2011b). The reason of this can be that all choirs practice is in progress in a place the center of city, easy reachable, safe places and times (Ardahan and Akdeniz, 2017b). The participants of amateur choirs mostly retired, so it

is easy to arrange reasonable time schedule for practicing. These also motivate individuals to participate more than one choir. Even if, there is women's hegemony in current study, man's running periods of choir is more than women. The reason of this can be the role of women in family life and the necessities on women shoulder (2011b). The results of current study support these conclusions. Man's Recognition and Social Status expectation is higher than women. This can be explained by Self Determination Theory (Deci and Ryan, 1985) and Self-Determination Theory (Dweck, 1986).

Türk-İş Labour Union declared that absolute poverty limits of 2016 as 1432 TL about 500\$^{vii}. The majority of CSGY has personal income and family income in poverty limit. But, CSGY pay due, willing to pay accessing to choir practice every two or three days in a week, and daily spending with this amount monthly personal and family income. In addition to these, CSGY spent average about four hours for practicing music in a choir. These can be the result of cohesion to music and choirs' atmosphere, or being choir singer is serious leisure activity for CSGY. This conclusion support Stebbins (1992) and Tipps (2003) determinations about amateur choirs.

There is positive correlation between income and LS. When personal and/or family income increases, LS level of CSGY increases also (Diener et al. 1985). The positive correlation between income and LS was confirmed in this study also. Age is main determiner of outdoor recreational activities. But for indoor activities age is not determiner. Participating choir as singer can be done in age. When age of CSGY increase, they want to participate in to choir for being away or escaping something/somewhere, recognition and getting social status. Young aged retired CSGY participate to choir for relaxing as mentally expectation.

Furthermore, the education level of majority CSGY in current study is high school and university graduation. Stebbins concluded that being well educated individuals has positive effect on informed choice and recreational priority and preferences (Stebbins, 2004). Ardahan realized this result in his study focus on volunteering (Ardahan, 2016c). In addition to education, aging also is another determiner of long running period. Tipps conclude that aged individuals usually never give up their recreational preferences and make sharp changes in their usual life Tibbs, 2003). The result of current study overlaps these conclusions. As education level and age increase, running period increases, too.

When people young usually they spent their time and energy in outdoor activities, aging decrease this year by year. The individuals in golden age usually prefer passive participation to the cultural and art activities, like watching TV, be with family, resting home, going to cinema or theatre (Ardahan, 2011b). The result overlaps with the findings of CSGY's recreational activities. But, they have active participation to amateur choir. It gives them pleasure and energy.

Contrary to what is believed, satisfactorily marriage motivates individuals for participating recreational activities alone and/or together (Ardahan, 2013). Participating choir is also, recreational activity. It is found that in current study, majority of CSGY were married and running alone, and married CSGY has more running period than

vii - http://www.teksif.org.tr/aralik-2016-aclik-ve-yoksulluk-siniri-1432-tl_icerik_10248-1.html, retrieved in 20/05/2017.

singles. This results overlaps with theoretic conclusion. Married CSGY's Exemplifying expectation from choir participation is higher than singles. This can be resulted from social roles of being parents or elders. There must be a connection between education level and exemplifying behavior. When education level decreases, exemplifying behavior, recognition and social status expectation of individuals increases.

Even if many of the CSGY were living with their family members, they prefer to run to choir alone. This is also same for mountaineer, rock climbers, fishermen, recreational bike user (Ardahan, 2013; Kaplan Kalkan and Ardahan, 2013; Ardahan and Turgut, 2013; Ardahan and Mert, 2014). Why this happen? It must be main goal of a new research.

Participating into a recreational activity requires one or more reason and it has positive effect on LS. The benefits show that realization of that reason. There is no statistically meaningful correlation between LS levels of retired CSGY and still working CSGY, but results of current study prove that participating into an amateur choir has positive effect on CSGY's LS level, when compared LS level of non-choir singers. When compared, there is also statistically meaningful correlation ($t=4.273$, $p<0.05$) with the LS levels of Kaplan Kalkan and Ardahan's study (2013). This means that participating recreational activity increase LS, but some of them has more effect on LS. In addition to these, the benefits of participating to amateur choir as CSGY have strong correlation with LS. The score of benefit "Felt Happier" is about 4.22 for retired CSGY, 4.26 for still working CSGY. These scores are really high score calculated on 5-point scale (Kaplan Kalkan and Ardahan, 2013; Ardahan and Mert, 2014; Weissinger and Bandalos, 1995; McKenzie, 2000; Rodriguez et al. 2008)

When individuals are retired, they lose their professional power and social relationship or social connection based on their professional life. This sometimes brings loneliness to individuals (Kilavuz, 2002; Sezer, 2011). Participating amateur choir has positive effect of socialization and give opportunity make new friendship. These help individuals for getting rid of loneliness. The result of current study overlaps this conclusion.

Even if majority of CSGY are running for one choir, people sometimes want to run more than one choir. There are many reasons for this. First; individuals can like to different music style, second; they can have enough time, money and other resources to support more than one choir, third; people have different social group and share time with them. In current study, CSGY participate more than one choir for getting more renovation/developing, to be away and/or escaping, and recognition and social status. This affects satisfaction level of participants.

5. Result

As a result of this study, for getting more happiness in golden years, singing in an amateur choir is a way. Singing makes happy individuals, increase their life satisfaction level. Motivational factors for singing in a choir are Liking Music, Relaxing as Mentally, Renovate and/or Developed, Socialization, Exemplifying, to be away and/or Escape,

and Recognition and Social status. All these factors create globally wellness and happiness in CSGY's life.

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